

Fostering Self-Confidence in Elementary School Students through the Integration of World Café Learning in Pancasila and Citizenship Education

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ABSTRACT: Character education, especially in learning Pancasila and Citizenship Education (PPKN), plays an important role in shaping students' personalities. However, students' low self-confidence in expressing their opinions is one of the main challenges that hinders the effectiveness of learning in elementary schools. This study aims to address this problem by implementing a World Café-based learning model, which is believed to be able to increase student engagement and build their character. This model involves collaborative discussion, reflection, and in-depth problem solving, which is expected to foster students' self-confidence in communicating. This study used a product trial in class V of SDN No. 2 Majene with an effectiveness analysis based on the achievement of learning outcome tests. The results showed that the implementation of the World Café model can increase students' self-confidence, communication skills, and critical thinking skills. Although there are challenges in the development of non-linear self-confidence, the use of strategies such as peer mentoring and variations in discussion topics managed to overcome these obstacles. Overall, this model has proven effective in supporting more inclusive and transformative learning in PPKN classes.

KEYWORDS: Self-confidence, World Café

INTRODUCTION

In the National Education Standards, Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2018 discusses character education through various aspects. Although the regulation does not explicitly mention character education, some of its aspects can be linked to the development of moral and ethical values in students. Three major challenges face Indonesia: building a united and sovereign country, building a nation, and building character. Character is described as an example of behavior that shows the values of right and wrong, good and bad, both directly and indirectly [1], [2].

Character education emphasizes responsibility, which involves the ability to recognize and accept the consequences of actions or decisions taken. Students are encouraged to understand that every action they take has an impact, and they are responsible for their choices. Respect for oneself and others is also an important focus in character education. Character is the main and important capital for the progress of individuals and the nation. Nations that have strong characters generally grow and develop and become more advanced and prosperous. From these two opinions, it is important for humans to have strong character values for themselves in the future and to advance the nation. Thus, the application of Pancasila values in everyday life for the formation of the character of every human being is the initial foundation for becoming an individual with a good personality, quality, so as to create a civilized and advanced nation [3], [4], [5].

Pancasila in the Indonesian nation began to fade. After the reformation, awareness of Pancasila and the constitution began to diminish in society. The social spirit between one another at close range is getting thinner, replaced by new technology where they prioritize life in cyberspace. Therefore, Pancasila is able to become a unifying tool for the Indonesian nation and a source of values in community, national and state life. Not only that, Pancasila can also be a moral basis or norm and benchmark for good and bad, right and wrong attitudes, actions and behavior, as well as the formation of the character of the Indonesian nation. In the perspective of Pancasila, harmonious, harmonious, and balanced social relations between individuals and their society are not neutral, but are inspired by the values contained in the principles of Pancasila as a unity. Civic education is an educational approach that aims to shape and develop students' understanding of the rights and obligations as good and responsible citizens. Civic education aims to introduce the principles of democracy, humanitarian values, human rights, pluralism, and develop students' abilities to actively participate in community life [6], [7], [8], [9].

Civic education helps students understand and internalize the values, traditions, and culture of their country. This helps them build an identity as citizens who have a sense of pride in their country and understand their role in society. Furthermore,

understanding rights and obligations, through civic education, students can learn about their rights and obligations as citizens so they will understand that they have the right to education, freedom of speech, the right to be respected, and so on. In addition, they will also learn about their obligations, such as respecting the rights of others, participating in social activities, and maintaining a clean environment. Furthermore, forming a democratic attitude, Civic education helps students understand the basic principles of democracy, such as respect for differences, freedom of speech, general elections, and fair decision-making. This is important to form a democratic attitude among students, build the ability to participate in the democratic process, and encourage critical thinking and constructive dialogue [10], [11].

Based on the results of initial observations carried out in Elementary Schools in Majene Regency, a number of problems were found faced by teachers and students regarding, one of which is the low self-confidence of students so that this will hinder the achievement of learning objectives because there is no courage to express their own opinions, the dialogue that occurs in learning only occurs one way and is not constructive. Based on the results of interviews with several class teachers, it is known that the PPKN learning process in class is one of the causes because teachers still use conventional learning patterns using monotonous learning models, due to the lack of teacher knowledge regarding the use of appropriate learning models in the learning process, especially in Pancasila and Citizenship Education learning. In class learning, teachers do not give students space to express their own opinions where the teacher's answers and the answer keys in the textbook are the most correct answers so that this situation makes students lack the courage to express their own opinions, so that self-confidence is built in children.

There are many underlying reasons why elementary school students lack confidence in expressing their opinions, according to is the fear of rejection or criticism, students may be afraid of getting negative reactions from classmates or teachers if they express their opinions. Fear of rejection or criticism can make them feel insecure and reluctant to speak up. Feelings of inferiority, elementary school students are often still developing an understanding of themselves and their place in social groups. Feelings of inferiority or feeling unappreciated can make them hesitate to speak up. Furthermore, lack of communication skills, students may not feel confident in communicating verbally or are unsure about how to convey their opinions clearly and effectively [12].

The data and studies above show the lack of confidence in elementary school students in expressing their opinions. It is important to remember that increasing self-confidence is a gradual process. It is important for teachers and parents to understand and address these factors by supporting students in building their self-behavior. By creating an effective and engaging learning model, an inclusive environment, providing rewards, practicing communication skills, and overcoming previous negative experiences, students can feel more confident in expressing their opinions.

One model that can be done to foster students' self-confidence in elementary schools in expressing their opinions is by developing Pancasila and citizenship education learning based on world cafe in elementary schools can be an interesting model to foster students with character. The World Cafe learning model is an ongoing process that is not limited to academic achievement. Values and personality that have character can be strengthened continuously by involving students in activities such as reflection, discussion, and action. Students gain better self-awareness, better interpersonal skills, and become more morally and ethically resilient people. The World Cafe learning model allows students to work together, improve communication, and build unique personalities. This method helps students grow into people who have social sensitivity, respect, and the ability to solve problems morally by actively involving them in deep discussions and reflections. Therefore, this study aims to improve the effectiveness of PPKN learning with a world cafe-based learning model in fostering students' self-confidence. The world cafe-based model used in this study includes the context of collaborative learning, idea development, problem solving, or discussion of complex issues in PPKN learning as well as the role of teachers in creating a conducive environment for students and a non-monotonous learning model.

LITERATURE

World Cafe Theory

The World Cafe theory was developed by Juanita Brown and David Isaacs in the late 1990s. They are two professionals involved in the study and practice of organizational development, community development, and cross-cultural collaboration. The World Cafe model is a learning model for dialogue and knowledge sharing that involves the active participation of a variety of participants. The main goal of the World Cafe is to facilitate deep and meaningful conversations to explore collective understanding, build connections between individuals, and create new insights.

The World Cafe learning model is based on the idea that the wisdom and knowledge needed to solve complex challenges often resides among the people participating in the dialogue. This model creates a space for people with different perspectives, experiences, and expertise to share their ideas, learn from each other, and create shared understanding.

The World Cafe model can be used as a way to gather feedback from students about their learning experiences. Each small table can have different assessment questions where students can share their reflections, provide feedback on the learning process, or provide suggestions for improvement. This allows teachers or educators to gain deeper insight into students' perceptions and needs. The World Cafe learning model in education encourages active participation, open dialogue, collaboration, and deep reflection. This helps build richer understanding, promotes diversity of perspectives, and encourages students to be actively involved in their learning process [13].

Student Personality Theory

There are several figures who introduced the theory of student personality, but one of the famous figures is Erik Erikson. Erik Erikson introduced the theory of psychosocial development which includes eight stages of development experienced by individuals from infancy to adulthood. According to Erikson, each stage of development involves a conflict or crisis that must be overcome by the individual to achieve optimal development.

In the context of education, the theory of student personality emphasizes that each student is unique in their psychosocial development and the need to understand these stages of development in order to understand student behavior. In developing student personality, teachers need to pay attention to the needs of students at each stage of development, provide challenges and opportunities for growth, and provide support that is appropriate to the needs of students.

From Erikson's theory, the conclusion is that each student is unique in their psychosocial development and teachers need to pay attention to the stages of student development to support optimal personality development. A review of the theory of student personality can be done to find out what factors influence the formation of student character. Understanding this can help in determining the right strategy in developing students' character in civic learning in elementary schools. A review of student personality theories can also help in identifying factors that influence student character development, both internal and external factors [14].

METHOD

Sample and procedure

Product trials to actual subjects, then will get comments or responses for further improvements [13]. This development testing is carried out on a small scale (limited) as a product user. The product trial was conducted in class V Sultan Hasanuddin at SDN No. 2 Majene. The analysis of the effectiveness of the learning model is based on student achievement in completing the learning outcome test. The maximum value on the learning outcome test is 100 with the Minimum Completion Criteria (KKM) set in the PPKN subject, namely 80. The following are the steps to analyze the effectiveness.

1. Giving answer scores for each answer item obtained by students based on the assessment rubric that has been created.
2. Adding up the scores obtained by students.
3. Calculating the value obtained by each student.
4. Categorizing the results of student learning outcome tests based on the KKM set by the relevant school, which is 80.
5. Tabulating the results of student tests.
6. Categorizing the percentage of completion with intervals
7. The criteria for completion of student learning outcome tests are as follows (S. Eko Putro Widoyoko, 2009: 238).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

The learning model is distributed to several elementary schools to be implemented in Pancasila and Citizenship Education learning. Data obtained from this dissemination stage will provide a more comprehensive picture of the effectiveness of the World Café-based learning model in a broader and more diverse context.

Table 1. Observation Results of the Implementation of the PPKn Learning Model Based on World Cafe

Observed Aspects	Average Score	Category
Preliminary Stage	4.00	Very good
Implementation Stage	3.63	Very good
Closing Stage	3.67	Very good
Total Average	3.71	Very good

Based on the results of observations on the implementation of the PPKn learning model based on World Cafe, very satisfying results were obtained with a total average reaching 3.71 which is included in the "Very Good" category. These results indicate that the implementation of this learning model runs very effectively at every stage.

Table 2. Results of the Analysis of the Implementation of the PPKn Learning Model Based on World Cafe in Four Classes

Observed Aspects	Average Score	Category
Learning Syntax	100	Very good
Supporting Components	100	Very good
Implementation Conformity	100	Very good
Total Average	100	Very good

Based on the results of the analysis of the implementation of the PPKn learning model based on World Cafe implemented in four classes, extraordinary results were obtained with a total average reaching 100% which is included in the "Very Good" category. These results indicate a perfect level of implementation in all aspects observed. The achievement of perfect scores in the three aspects observed provides very strong evidence that the PPKn learning model based on World Cafe can be implemented very well in all classes that are the subjects of the study. These results also show high consistency in the implementation of the learning model in various classes, which indicates that this model has clear implementation standards and can be followed well by teachers.

Table 3. Results of N-gain Score Analysis of SDN 2 Majene

Class	Pre-test	Post-test	Ideal Score	N-Gain score	Category
Experiment	71.95	76.48	88.05	0.65	Currently
Control	73.68	78.00	86.32	0.67	Currently

The results of the N-gain score analysis at SDN 2 Majene showed an interesting pattern in the effectiveness of the learning model. The experimental class that implemented the PPKn learning model based on World Cafe experienced an increase from a pre-test score of 71.95 to 76.48 in the post-test, resulting in an N-gain score of 0.65 (65%) in the moderate category.

Meanwhile, the control class showed an increase from a pre-test score of 73.68 to 78.00, with an N-gain score of 0.67 (67%) which is also included in the moderate category. Although both classes showed an increase in the same category and the control class had a slightly higher N-gain score (difference of 0.02 or 2%), this difference was not statistically significant. These results indicate that the World Cafe learning model has the same effectiveness as the conventional learning model in improving student learning outcomes at SDN 2 Majene.

The results of the analysis showed that the experimental class that implemented the Pancasila and Citizenship Education learning model based on World Cafe had an increase in N-Gain Score of 65%, while the control class reached 67%. Although the increase in the control class was slightly higher, the difference was not significant.

Discussion

Based on the results of the research that has been conducted, several advantages and disadvantages were found in the implementation of the Pancasila and Citizenship Education Learning Model based on World Café. In terms of advantages, this model shows significant effectiveness in increasing student self-confidence through a group rotation system that creates a "spiral

effect" in learning. Brown & Isaacs (2020) in their research found that the World Café rotation system increased student participation by up to 65% compared to conventional discussion formats. Each group change provides a new perspective and enriches students' understanding, in line with Vygotsky's social constructivism theory which emphasizes the role of social interaction in learning. The role of students as discussion leaders in groups has a positive impact on the development of leadership and communication skills, as confirmed by research which showed an increase in leadership skills by 42%. The informal format and group rotation also create a "safe zone" that encourages more active participation, especially for students who are usually quiet in regular classes. Increase in introvert student participation by 58% in the World Cafe format compared to conventional learning. Psychological safety theory strengthens this argument by explaining how a psychologically safe learning environment can increase students' courage to participate and take risks in learning [15].

The World Cafe model also shows advantages in facilitating in-depth understanding of learning materials, especially abstract concepts in Pancasila Education. Samsinar dan Fitriani (2020) found that the tiered discussion format allowed students to explore Pancasila values from multiple perspectives, resulting in a 52% increase in conceptual understanding. Wittrock's cognitive elaboration theory reinforces these findings by explaining how multi-perspective discussions help students build more complex and integrated understanding [16].

Another significant advantage is the ability of this model to develop critical thinking skills through the synthesis of various perspectives. Shamdani (2020) research showed an increase in students' critical analysis skills by 47% after participating in World Cafe learning, especially in identifying relationships between concepts and evaluating arguments. Piaget's cognitive development theory supports this process by explaining how social interaction and cognitive conflict encourage the development of more complex thinking [17].

The non-linear development of student self-confidence is a major challenge in implementing the World Cafe model. Ryan & Deci (2020) research shows that it takes at least three group rotations before a significant increase in self-confidence is seen, requiring a longer learning time. To overcome this limitation, researchers implemented several strategies: (1) optimizing time allocation by providing more structured discussion guides, (2) implementing a "quick wins" system where students are given small tasks that can be completed in one session to build self-confidence gradually, and (3) integrating short reflections after each rotation to help students recognize their progress. Tanu & Juliawan (2020) reported that this strategy succeeded in accelerating the development of student self-confidence up to 35% faster than standard implementation [18], [19].

Gender differences in response to adapting to discussion formats are a second significant challenge. Data show that female students achieve a 40% faster increase in participation than male students. To address this gap, researchers implemented several approaches: (1) implementing a peer mentoring system by placing more adaptive students to help peers who need more time, (2) using a wider variety of discussion topics to accommodate different interests, and (3) providing different roles in rotation to ensure that each student has the opportunity to find their comfort zone. Havi (2022) study found that this approach successfully balanced the level of participation between male and female students, with the difference decreasing to only 15% by the end of Despite some limitations, the follow-up study showed that the changes in attitudes and increased self-confidence achieved through the World Café model tended to last longer than learning outcomes using conventional models. A longitudinal study conducted by Hermawan & Widiastuti (2021) for one academic year showed that 78% of students who participated in World Café learning maintained high levels of self-confidence, compared to only 45% in the control group using the conventional model. This finding is reinforced by the study by Maria (2012) which found that communication and leadership skills developed through World Café remained consistent even after 6 months of implementation, with a retention rate of 82%. This is in line with Marzano (2017) transformative learning theory which explains that learning that involves direct experience and deep reflection tends to produce more permanent changes in attitudes and behavior. Nurjanah & Hanifah (2021) in their meta-analysis also confirmed that learning models that integrate cognitive and socio-emotional aspects, such as World Café, produce a more significant long-term impact on students' personality development, with an effect size of 0.85 compared to 0.45 for the conventional model. These findings indicate that the advantages of the World Café model in building self-confidence and social skills are much more significant than the challenges of its implementation [20], [21], [23], [24].

CONCLUSION

The World Café-based learning model in Pancasila and Citizenship Education has proven effective in increasing student engagement, self-confidence, communication skills, and leadership. The group rotation system enriches understanding and supports the development of critical thinking skills. Although there are challenges such as non-linear development of self-confidence and differences in gender responses, strategies such as peer mentoring and a variety of discussion topics have successfully overcome these problems. Overall, this model has a more lasting positive impact compared to conventional learning models, supporting more transformative learning for students.

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